

Novel peptide nucleic acids for recognition of double-stranded RNA

Version 1

Description

Recently we have developed a peptide nucleic acid (PNA) and double-stranded RNA (dsRNA) triplex computational model. Implementation of molecular dynamics simulations, based on our triplex model resulted in discovery of original and effective PNA nucleobase for recognition of CG base pair in RNA. During the course of PhD research, we are planning to further develop computational techniques for the design of more selective PNA nucleobases with higher affinity and stability at physiological pH. The main goal is to create a universal set of PNA nucleobases for recognition of any dsRNA base pair in any dsRNA sequence. This will allow to create an important tool for molecular recognition of regulatory RNA and to control its biological functions.

Funder

Central Finance and Contracting Agency

Grant

Novel peptide nucleic acids for recognition of double-stranded RNA

Researchers

Vladislavs Baškevičs (orcid:0000-0001-5489-6760)

Organizations

Latvijas Organiskās Sintēzes Institūts

1. Main Info

Title of DMP: [Novel peptide nucleic acids for recognition of double-stranded RNA](#)

Description:

Recently we have developed a peptide nucleic acid (PNA) and double-stranded RNA (dsRNA) triplex computational model. Implementation of molecular dynamics simulations, based on our triplex model resulted in discovery of original and effective PNA nucleobase for recognition of CG base pair in RNA. During the course of PhD research, we are planning to further develop computational techniques for the design of more selective PNA nucleobases with higher affinity and stability at physiological pH. The main goal is to create a universal set of PNA nucleobases for recognition of any dsRNA base pair in any dsRNA sequence. This will allow to create an important tool for molecular recognition of regulatory RNA and to control its biological functions.

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[Vladislavs Baškevičs \(orcid:0000-0001-5489-6760\)](#)

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2. Funding

Funding organizations: [Central Finance and Contracting Agency](#)

Grants: [Novel peptide nucleic acids for recognition of double- stranded RNA](#)

Project: [Novel peptide nucleic acids for recognition of double- stranded RNA](#)

3. License

License: [CC-BY-4.0](#)

Access Rights: [Public](#)

Publication Date: [2025-12-17](#)

4. Templates

Descriptions

LCS FARP

Data Management Plan | Novel peptide nucleic acids for recognition of double-stranded RNA

Template: LCS FARP

Type: Dataset

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

To share scientific data

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

Experimental data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

PDF

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

5

MB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.6 If No, please describe, if you have considered re-using any of existing data?

No

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

Researchers

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

Yes

DOI

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

No

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

3 Resources and Security

Powered by

